

Changing research incentives in practice: lessons from institutional experiments

Annex - Full text case studies

CASE STUDY 1

A comprehensive funders' strategy to steer cultural change in research assessment - FNR (Luxembourg)

The [Luxembourg National Research Fund \(FNR\)](#) is the main funder of research activities in the country, investing public funds and private donations into research projects in various branches of science and the humanities. Sean Sapcariu is a biomedical research Programme Manager at FNR, promoting changes in research culture towards more open, impactful and collaborative work. FNR was one of the early institutions piloting narrative CVs.

In 2020, the Wellcome Trust published a study with over 4,000 participants which exposed a culture of bullying and harassment in research. After reading this report, Sean Sapcariu started thinking about what could be done to change research culture from a funder's perspective. Sean works as a programme manager at FNR but on top of his responsibilities in the biomedical domain he dedicates time to design, implement and evaluate changes in research culture.

The project: Envisioning a comprehensive strategy

Funds allocation for open science

Mirroring experiences of other research funders, FNR runs the Open Access Fund programme to promote free access to research results from FNR-(co)funded projects. It provides financial support to cover article processing charges, helping researchers to comply with the [FNR Open Access Policy](#).

Sean is very clear on recognising that open science goes beyond open access to publications, and that often researchers find themselves in the middle of a fight between funders and publishers regarding open access. To ensure that other open science activities can be supported, since 2022 FNR has created a budget category for open science (see [category 6.8.4](#)). This means that open science expenses as part of FNR projects are now eligible for reimbursement.

The goal is to keep this funding pot as flexible as possible. “We want to incentivise people to think about open science as something that is recognised by the funder, and that they now have money for” says Sean. The funds can't pay salaries, but could pay for example consultants in software development, training, outreach & engagement with society, to name a few.

Narrative CVs

Originally created by the Royal Society (UK) together with the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), the narrative-based CV seeks to widen the range of things which researchers and innovators are valued for.

In 2019, the FNR introduced the [narrative CV template](#), which came into effect in 2021, for Principal Investigators (PIs) and Co-PIs requesting funding from FNR programmes. The goal of the narrative-style CV is to allow an applicant to be more fairly evaluated on their scientific vision, appropriate experience, and a broader set of contributions to science and society (including those related to responsible research conduct, Open Science, mentoring, and others), instead of solely metrics, journal names, and other information that does not fully represent the potential of a researcher.

Mentorship opportunities

The [Peer Exchange Platform for Narrative-style CVs](#) (PEP-CV) is a resource for the research and innovation community developed by a partnership between funding agencies and researchers.

The goal of PEP-CV is to become a platform for everyone active in the research and innovation sector to engage in simple peer mentoring exchanges. The goal is to discuss how to best present a diverse range of experiences, achievements, and career paths in all types of narrative-style CVs.

The call for mentors is currently open, the initiative will be launched officially in Spring 2024. Mentees will be able to connect with mentors from a broad range of traditional and non-traditional career pathways in research. Through mentorship, mentees will be able to better articulate their work for evaluation, hiring and promotion purposes.

Gaining support for change

Funders have a unique chance to drive change; experiments in research incentives may be resisted initially, but changing research culture is urgent. Sean approaches the discussion from a values perspective. *“As a national funder we should agree on the values that are important to us, and align our strategies to reflect that in practice”*.

The size of Luxembourg’s research community provides an interesting opportunity for faster change. FNR signed DORA and CoARA initiatives, which Sean agrees are important for buying leadership support and aligning values in the right direction. FNR and DORA have worked together in publishing a [resource for funders](#) aiming to improve research assessment.

In terms of implementation, Sean mentions there is still a need for concrete strategies and sharing the lessons of experiments between funders. Participating in Science Europe, the association representing major public research organizations in the continent, particularly the exchange during working groups on research culture, proved to be of great value for his work.

Evaluating change

Of all three strategies, the funds allocation and the mentorship platform are the most recent ones. Changes in funds allocation in 2022 apply to 5-year research projects. Sean mentions that it will be interesting to understand how researchers are using those funds for open science, collecting ideas on concrete applications that can be then amplified throughout the funding pipeline.

To date, the narrative CV initiative has produced [two assessments](#), in 2021 and 2023. After the first

assessment, some changes to the initiative include:

- changing its name to “Individual Narrative Profile” to move away from the perception of a “CV” (as it is more quantitative/list),
- word counts and prescriptive structure were removed, focusing only on a 2 page limit for the document;
- online resources from other funders and institutions were added to provide applicants with more assistance in filling out the document,
- guidance was modified to show applicants that outputs in all areas are not expected,
- minor wording changes were made to help clarify expectations, request evidence where possible, and expand the definition of some of the sections.

The 2023 survey had a 31.69% response rate from applicants and 47.61% response rate from reviewers. 63% of applicants found the narrative profile to be generally positive, with 30% feeling neutral, and 7% with a negative perspective. This result shows a positive shift from 2021 (48% positive, 33% neutral, 19% negative), showing a trend towards further acceptance of the narrative profile. While the overall trend was positive, there were differences in the perception and feedback of the narrative profile based on gender and domain.

A significant insight, reviewers did not perceive evaluation of the narrative CV to be longer or more complicated than a traditional CV, refuting one of the most common critical points raised by researchers around the topic of narrative-style CVs.

A common theme around narrative CVs is the request for examples. Specific help around how to write the document is also requested. Very detailed guidance however may be in conflict with the concept of the narrative-style CV being personalized and tailored. There is also a worry that narrative-style CVs would give an unfair advantage to those with better “storytelling” skills. Reviewer’s perspectives on guidance and training also show the need for better and more explicit guidelines on how to use narrative profiles in evaluation.

FNR also participates in a [research project](#) assessing the impact of various institutions piloting the Narrative-CV, led by the Research on Research Institute (RoRI).

Sustaining change

Although funders can drive significant changes in research culture, challenges arise when working with other stakeholders, such as universities. Researchers may find themselves trying to respond to two different assessment frameworks at the same time. As funders push for narrative CVs, universities still assess research based on quantitative indicators and international rankings. “We aim to harmonize these practices, but it is a slow process” – Sean mentions, sharing that one university has agreed to start piloting narrative CVs soon.

The work behind driving this change from inside the funder is demanding on Sean’s time, and actually not in scope of his programme manager role. Transmitting enthusiasm about it, he mentions that his colleagues at FNR are now thinking about changing research culture as a possibility, coming up with new ideas and discussions. An example is a potential collaboration with the [Luxembourg National Data Service](#), to better recognize and reward open science work in the realm of open source software which is currently underrepresented. He also leads a CoARA working group aiming to collect “crazy ideas in research assessment” that can inform future pilots.

Overall, Sean is optimistic about the impact of these changes. “The first signs of cultural change can be found in language, or how people talk about their work” he says. He highlights how during the FNR Awards, people now talk more about teamwork, collaboration, impact, rather than papers and publishing. “It is something

worth analyzing in the future, how conversations are changing towards openness and collaboration” and the way these strategies are making a better research culture.

CASE STUDY 2

Facilitating more open & equitable research evaluation through infrastructure changes at the BIH QUEST Center (Berlin, Germany)

The QUEST Center at the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH) @Charité develops and implements novel approaches to support that biomedical research is conducted in a trustworthy manner, provides useful results, and meets ethical standards.

Miriam Kip joined QUEST in 2017 as an officer for incentives and indicators. She currently leads the [research incentives working group](#), including a project that developed a software portal to transform how professorship applications are evaluated at Charité and BIH.

Background

The QUEST Center was initially called “QUEST Center for Transforming Biomedical Research”, signaling its aim to evaluate existing incentive systems and indicators within the biomedical research landscape, among many other activities. Its primary goal was to transition towards a more responsible and science-based system, addressing issues such as fairness, competition, and the quality of research outputs. This responded to the need for mitigating negative consequences of excessive focus on quantity over quality, or the detrimental effects of careerism, where individual success hinders collaboration.

At the time of creation, the institute’s Dean and Prof. Dimagl, head of the QUEST center, had already made changes in the evaluation process for appointing professors. These included five new areas: the candidate's contribution to open science, to team sciences, the candidate’s selection of top five publications irrespective of authorship position, an impact narrative on their scientific contribution, and academic age.

The assessment and selection processes are complex; the use and weight of indicators can sometimes be less or more explicit. When Miriam Kip joined in 2017, applicants had to submit individual applications for professorships that included their publication record, third party funding, and other conventional criteria. At least during preselection, the main criteria for assessment of candidates was the number of publications, the impact factor and h-index, and the amount of third-party funding obtained.

Framing the problem

Evaluators are mostly professors, including a student representative and an equal opportunity representative as well as a disability representative. Evaluators received emails containing attachments for each application or were able to access the individual application files via a shared institutional file system. Additionally, they received password-protected overviews listing applicants' details such as age, name, gender, third-party funding, number of publications, and H-index. This information was condensed in large tables to aid in pre-selection meetings where evaluators negotiate which applicants to invite for interviews.

Miriam Kip began observing and supporting these processes, mostly about the uptake and usability of the newly introduced indicators. The team quickly realized that the table format, though pragmatic, became impractical when it exceeded one page, making it difficult for evaluators to recall or compare information effectively.

The team looked at how much evaluators were open to new assessment dimensions such as open science or robustness of research. They could observe that usually a question around open science or collaboration was indeed incorporated into the assessment protocol. Second, when applicants participated in the interviews, their background was much richer than what their application had shown. This trend was particularly strong in areas like patient engagement or stakeholder engagement, which are often considered of lesser scientific value by some professionals. Open science practices or funding from industry were also at times considered something irrelevant or a conflict of interest. Finally, there were naturalized biases related to personal connections or country/region of origin of the new applicants.

The first approach was to address these problems by creating new tables. However, the team quickly realized there was no way a conventional Excel spreadsheet or a PDF document could work. As a research assistant at the time had just learned about dashboards using Shiny, the team developed a prototype shiny app for reviewers to have more efficient access to the candidates' information.

About the project

Most transformations in research assessment are referred to as cultural change. Though this can be true, Dr. Kip does not necessarily fully agree with it: "If change is cultural, it is hard to capture and understand its effectiveness and direction". The infrastructure approach, on the other hand, has allowed the team to detect if change is happening or not through evaluation of uptake and adoption. This does not mean infrastructure change is completely bottom-up. Dr. Kip highlights: "this project only exists because the very top has decided that change should happen and we have great support within QUEST". Subscribing to initiatives like DORA, or now more recently CoARA helped to gain this support.

Rather than dictating choices, the team's goal is to offer reflective tools to reviewers that help explain the origins, strengths, and limitations of each assessment criterion. There is no imposition of specific criteria, such as determining the domain of field experts. The focus lies in facilitating expert peer review through a structured and systematic approach.

To this end, the portal provides a comprehensive set of science-based criteria aimed at reducing bias and enhancing the quality of review, aligning the criteria with the mission of Charité and BIH. Many indicators that already existed are now made explicit, including science communication, teaching concepts, diversity, equity, inclusion, and open science contributions. The design prioritizes quality over quantity, emphasizing qualitative assessment before quantitative indicators. The selection of indicators and functionalities is based on literature, best-practice recommendations and policies and alignment with institutional practices and requirements.

The candidates' information is made available via a structured, narrative CV that the applicants provide online through the application tool of the MERIT portal. Applications are accessible only after exclusion of conflict of interests and then default to anonymized views, encouraging thoughtful consideration and mitigating implicit biases by shifting them to explicit awareness.

Gaining support for change

The prototype that the team developed in Shiny allowed the team to explore technical integration with the portal people were already using. This aided displaying it to various stakeholders including the Dean, faculty members, and the Berlin medical Senate. The positive feedback spurred further development.

The project initially received funding support from the Wellcome Trust for developing the prototype further. Recognizing the need for sustainability, the team then secured funding from QUEST and BIH, totaling 140,000 euros, to transform the prototype into a comprehensive software suite. With the assistance of a dedicated developer the prototype was professionalized. The portal was revamped, enhancing indicators, and dedicated software was built for management and review of applications. The resulting package caters to the diverse needs of three user groups: applicants, managers and reviewers, ensuring functionality and usability across the board.

Laying the ground for change: implementation of a new tool

After the initial changes in criteria were implemented, the application portal contained better information for assessment, but there was uncertainty about how hiring commissions utilized this information in decision-making processes. The inefficiency of the procedure, presenting information through lengthy PDF documents, meant that relevant information was not seen and supported biases in selection of candidates. The aim of Dr. Kip's team was to make the new criteria more accessible: digitalization used to provide structure for responsible indicators, leveraging strategies to mitigate bias and enhance fairness.

The approach focused on offering a tool to streamline the review process without imposing specific changes in criteria. Emphasizing technical advancements and support tools, the goal was to empower evaluators with information and structure to improve peer-review, while respecting their autonomy and expertise.

Avoiding a prescriptive approach was key to recognizing the independence and hierarchical dynamics within academic institutions. While some people may resist change until mandated, the aim of the project is to facilitate informed decision-making rather than enforcing transformation. The team thinks this is the way to make change easier to accept: "No one likes to be told what to do, but it is harder to resist change if it makes your life easier" says Dr. Kip.

Navigating bureaucratic change

The initiative is a prioritized project in the portfolio of Charité for the past one and a half years. This has presented numerous challenges and opportunities. Initially, securing access and collaboration commitments was a significant hurdle for the team. Navigating the bureaucratic maze within the institution has proved daunting, requiring the team to learn and adapt at each step. Although the IT department at the institute can perfectly support ongoing projects, there are limited resources and infrastructure for emerging ones, which adds layers of complexity to the process.

With initially limited IT support, the team forged its own path, from considering server applications to dealing with software maintenance agreements. Dr. Kip's background is in health and research policy and research assessment. This meant there was no previous experience in software development in the team. "Balancing administrative tasks, funding management and stakeholder coordination has been overwhelming", she mentions. The absence of dedicated support from a project manager or technical support was noticeable; however, the current reality demands meticulous attention to detail and exhaustive efforts in implementation with available resources.

The team envisions delegating responsibilities and fostering collaboration with a supportive, broader structure – ideally across institutions using the portal. Dr. Kip considers a collaboration with other groups with similar views in terms of infrastructure changes for research assessment could alleviate some of the burden and contribute fresh perspectives.

Educating stakeholders about the complexities of software development and implementation remains a constant endeavor. It is challenging to convey the time and effort required, particularly in the face of resistance and skepticism. Dr. Kip closes with a hopeful note: “though the journey was demanding and exhausting at times and despite the hurdles, we have made considerable progress”.

Managing expectations

Navigating perceptions and expectations regarding innovative technology like the MERIT Portal has been a recurring challenge. Users often misinterpret its functions and assume it performs tasks autonomously, which leads to misunderstandings during pitches and discussions. Despite efforts to clarify the software aim, confusion persists.

During this process, Dr. Kip realized that reviewers are more focused in having quick, pragmatic processes rather than in other aspects of assessment such as robustness. However, maintaining the portal’s role as a tool for insight rather than automatic decision-making is crucial for the project. The team aims to empower users with flexibility in utilizing the tool, not pushing for automated reviews.

Clarifying these distinctions and managing expectations effectively is an ongoing process. It is essential to address assumptions and preconceptions proactively, ensuring users understand the portals' intended purpose and functionality accurately. Through engaging with stakeholders, the team also found many supporters inside the institutions, sometimes in unexpected places. There is significant internal support, for example from the data protection team, individual researchers, or the IT department, but also encouraging words and guidance. This shared enthusiasm is an important driver to continue to finalize the product despite the hurdles and without a clear, predictable outcome. The MERIT Portal for appointments will now be piloted in a hiring procedure and available as open source software.

Evaluating change

The team initially pitched the project to the Dean and potential reviewers, who were all enthusiastic and mentioned a project like this should have been in place a long time ago, saving time and effort. Test applicants have provided encouraging feedback about the MERIT Portal. First, it took them some time to restructure their own thinking about their careers and how to present this information. One applicant mentioned they now feel that somebody is really interested in what they did, and that actually somebody is going to read it.

A formal pilot starts in May 2024. The portal was first tested internally to check robustness; currently there is a pilot hiring running. The team also plans to conduct an anonymous survey after the hiring meeting, including usability aspects and suggestions of other indicators that reviewers would like to see. Applicants will also test it to gather feedback on their experience. Overall, the team aims to get feedback from all three user groups: applicants, reviewers, and managers.

The team is also considering running a mock process with a fake hiring procedure that can afterwards allow comparison of time taken and candidate selection output, with or without the portal. These are still in the planning phase.

Sustaining change

Implementing these changes takes time and it's very institution-specific but Dr. Kip is confident in this approach. “If you implement changes very quickly and without this process, you might spend a lot of money on something that is never going to be used” she mentions. There are commercial products that try to also capture the niche of assessment needs. The MERIT Portal aims to provide a solution that is dynamic, easily adaptable and affordable overtime, because it has been developed within the public research system and is based on in-depth knowledge of the relevant aspects and processes.

Having people at the institution who are deeply involved in the development process of the software is key. It is then informed by the needs and requirements from the user, maintains flexibility and it is less dependent on a company, avoiding potential vendor lock-in. As this is an open source development coming from public service, there is an opportunity for transferring and sharing so institutions don't have to reinvent the wheel each time.

One key aspect to consider was licensing. As is the case in most research institutions, everything that is developed during working time belongs to the institution. In terms of the tech transfer, as the MERIT portal is not a medical product it does not have a “significant value” in a monetary sense. This makes it easier to openly license it, but it also meant the project was not eligible for existing intramural funding lines due to being “out of scope”. The tech transfer supported the project in finding an adequate open-source license for the software.

The project's interest was not to make profit out of the development. Instead, they aim to find a sustainable way for supporting the portal and connecting to others using it. A white-label version will be released open source, without specific structural information for security reasons. It will be hosted on GitHub so others can download it, install it on premise or using a cloud solution, and adapt it according to their specific requirements. Except for security relevant aspects, new functionalities or contributions will have to be made available under the same open source license.

Dr. Kip thinks the future is bright for the MERIT project. “We would love to have a community or a nonprofit organization around the project that brings people together and fosters new developments”, she mentions. Having many small contributions from institutions using the portal could help sustain the project financially and technically, benefiting all stakeholders.

CASE STUDY 3

Recognizing open source contributions in promotions - Monash University (Australia)

The Econometrics & Business Statistics Department at Monash University hosts an active group of data scientists producing some of the most used open source software packages in the field. A lack of recognition for this development work led Professor [Rob Hyndman](#) to promote a policy change so junior researchers face a different reality. It aims to reward high quality open source software contributions as part of the promotion process.

Rob Hyndman has developed open source software for statistical science for 30 years. He is motivated by a passion for it, despite a lack of formal recognition. Now a Professor of Statistics in the [Department of Econometrics and Business Statistics](#) at [Monash University](#), he observed junior members of his Department suffering from the same lack of recognition for their open source developments.

About the project

Three years ago, Hyndman proposed to the Monash Business School that there should be a policy in place to recognize open source software contributions in promotions. After an initial proposal underwent several iterations, the final version aimed to ensure that software contributions would be peer-reviewed similarly to academic papers, ensuring quality and credibility.

The proposal required that software be peer-reviewed, preferably by external organizations like CRAN or rOpenSci, and fully open-sourced in repositories such as GitHub, GitLab, or Bitbucket. Contributors needed to provide documentation detailing their contributions. A committee would review the proposals, assigning points based on quality, similar to the system used for academic publications. Software contributions could earn up to three points, equivalent to high-quality journal papers, emphasizing quality over quantity.

The proposal was approved in late 2021 after about two years of development. A committee including external members from the University of Auckland and a university in the US, plus Hyndman, oversee the policy implementation. As promotion rounds typically occur later in the year, they are expecting submissions will come in as the policy becomes more established.

Gaining support

The proposal didn't face significant resistance, but required extensive explanation. Initially, many questioned the need for a new policy, suggesting that researchers could simply publish their software in existing journals like the R Journal, the Journal of Statistical Software, or the Journal of Open Source Software.

It was key to communicate that software contributions should be evaluated separately from academic papers about the software. While a paper might discuss the software, the software itself should be assessed independently. This distinction was crucial, as the value of the software might not be fully reflected in the paper's evaluation. The process was prolonged mainly due to the university's slow bureaucratic procedures. The proposal needed to pass through numerous committees and obtain approval from the union and senior HR because it impacted the promotion criteria and the enterprise agreement.

Despite the delays, there was general goodwill towards the initiative, partly because of Hyndman's established reputation in the faculty for widely used software. The faculty recognized the benefits of supporting software development, acknowledging that almost everyone benefited from open source software packages for our work, except for the creators. Then this policy could provide better career paths for future researchers in similar positions.

Making change happen

Regarding software peer review, the policy acknowledges that if the code has been approved by CRAN or ROpenSci, that information would be valuable for the assessment committee. However, the committee plans to conduct a careful review as well. They anticipate using the guidelines from rOpenSci for software

evaluation and asking reviewers to provide reports based on those standards. Hyndman is an executive editor of the R Journal and a section editor of the Journal of Statistical Software, where referees are requested to review both the paper and the associated software following brief guidelines. The committee might adopt a similar approach.

Beyond the top-down approach, researchers developing open source software at Monash University actively promote development among students. They organize joint research group meetings and hackathons to enhance skills and encourage PhD students to incorporate open-source software projects into their theses. Additionally, master's and advanced undergraduate students can take the course "Advanced R Programming," aiming to elevate their coding skills.

Some PhD students have also become involved in teaching software development, with a few attending The Carpentries courses to become certified trainers. However, participation in these courses varies. Despite this, the overall trend indicates a growing emphasis on providing resources and training opportunities for students to develop their software development skills, reflecting a broader commitment within the research group to foster a culture of open-source software development and proficiency.

Challenges

A common issue for recognizing academic open source software development is the lack of effort in making code generalizable to different datasets. This often results in software that is narrowly tailored to specific problems. Additionally, there's a problem with the maintenance of software packages, where authors may not commit to long-term upkeep, leading to packages being removed from platforms like CRAN due to failing tests. This underscores the significant effort required to maintain software effectively, which often goes unrewarded in traditional academic evaluation criteria.

Another challenge lies in the development of user interfaces. Hyndman highlights that researchers may excel in methodology and coding, but most lack skills in designing intuitive user interfaces. This results in research software that may be clunky or difficult to use, hindering its adoption. Research software engineers could potentially address this issue; there's a scarcity of such resources within the department.

Scaling issues are prevalent, with some software packages struggling to handle large datasets, prompting users to migrate to alternative platforms like Python for improved performance. Commercial software providers like SAS may also lag in implementing modern techniques due to a lack of user demand, highlighting a disconnect between developers' responsibilities to educate users and the commercial incentives driving software development.

Sustaining change

Some funders in Europe and the US have started addressing the software sustainability problem through the creation of the "research software engineer (RSE)" role. Hyndman mentions that a policy that recognizes open source development is crucial in this direction. Without such a policy, RSEs often remain in long-term postdoc positions with limited prospects for promotion since traditional criteria only focus on papers and conferences.

The presence of an RSE in a research group is invaluable for ensuring that software meets high standards, thereby making research outputs more usable and impactful. Policies that recognize and reward the

contributions of RSEs can provide them with better career opportunities and prevent migration to the private sector.

For now, Hyndman mentions his department's approach to maintenance: hiring a skilled software developer using consulting income. This method, though effective, is not scalable. A more sustainable solution could involve establishing funds or foundations to support key tools' development and maintenance. For example, organizations like the R Consortium, funded by large companies, could potentially provide grants to maintain essential software packages, ensuring their continued usability even when original maintainers are unavailable.

Funders are increasingly supporting the development of software packages like R or Python in grant proposals. However, often the applicants lack the necessary experience to produce high-quality software. Hyndman mentions that funding agencies could address this by employing RSEs to assist in both the development and maintenance of these tools. Providing funding for a set period, such as five years, could ensure the longevity and usability of the software, ultimately benefiting the whole research community.

CASE STUDY 4

Open Source Program Offices enabling research impact - Carnegie Mellon University (USA)

The Open Source Program Office at Carnegie Mellon University (CMU) serves as a first point of contact for open-source at CMU, while building strong relationships with the private sector to amplify the impact of open source software. [Sayeed Choudhury](#), Director of the OSPO, shares how it is embedded within CMU's structure, and its approach to nurturing, tracking and recognizing academic open source software work.

Universities, funders, research organizations like CERN: everyone is increasingly looking at open source software as a primary research object, considering its impacts in research reproducibility and sustainability to name a few. With the advent of open science, funders' requirements for publications and data are clear. But including open source software as part of open science is not as straightforward.

Sayeed Choudhury, Director of the Open Source Programs Office (OSPO) at Carnegie Mellon Libraries, highlights the multiple differences between communities and practices within open science. Faculty are often more comfortable sharing their software on GitHub and other platforms than their data. There is less orientation internally on how to share software but long-standing communities online, so researchers are more open to ask for help. The relationship with the private sector is also different. So, how can universities and research institutions incentivize open source work, bringing their voice back into the open source conversation?

About the project

The concept of an Open Source Programs Office (OSPO) has been prevalent in the private sector but is relatively new to universities. Carnegie Mellon University (CMU) is among the first wave of universities to establish such an office. The primary mission of CMU's OSPO is to improve the identification, management, curation, and sharing of open-source software within the university. Acting as a competency center, it serves

as a first contact point for open-source inquiries and coordinates resources and expertise across the institution.

The OSPO at CMU is directed by a team of two. Choudhury focuses on external partnerships and broader impacts of open source on infrastructure, policy, and technology; a community manager, Tom Hughes, fosters internal community support among faculty and students. The office assists in proposal submissions, directly supports projects, and facilitates services like GitHub Enterprise.

The OSPO was initiated by the dean of libraries through a successful funding proposal to the Sloan Foundation. It was the internal advocacy by the dean, engaging with university leadership, that ensured the establishment of the OSPO, indicating it would likely have been realized even without external funding. In fact, CMU has allocated ongoing funding for both Choudhury and Hughes.

Gaining support

One of the early messages that Choudhury had to communicate was that the OSPO is not there to mandate that all research should be open-sourced. Instead, its role is to help faculty explore open source as an option, without imposing it as a requirement. This alleviated initial concerns about potential concerns with other departments, such as the tech transfer office.

There is common ground between the OSPO and tech transfer's goal of translating and disseminating CMU's research outputs, whether for commercial or social impact. This collaborative approach has allowed both offices to address faculty needs more effectively, directing them to the appropriate expert for specific issues. The OSPO also integrates open source into CMU's broader open science initiatives. This integration ensures a cohesive support structure for open-source projects across the university.

The OSPO at CMU, while part of the library's open science program, maintains a unique and flexible identity. This dual affiliation is advantageous, as it allows it to draw on the library's resources and credibility while also operating independently when beneficial. The OSPO's affiliation with the library provides a solid foundation, but its distinct role and approach allow it to effectively address the specific needs of open-source projects within the university, e.g. when fundraising.

Navigating change

The OSPO at CMU emerged on fertile soil; open-source software is widely embraced across various disciplines at CMU, from computer science and engineering to the humanities, arts, and architecture. There is little resistance to open-source software; rather, the response ranges from enthusiastic support to acceptance.

However, with the establishment of any new office at a university, there is always curiosity and questions about its purpose and impact. To address this, it was crucial to clearly define the office's scope and limitations. For instance, the OSPO does not advise on commercializing work, which helps maintain clear boundaries and foster better collaboration with other university departments such as tech transfer, legal, and research administration.

Early on, it was key to engage in continuous dialogue with various stakeholders to outline the OSPO role and seek their input on how to coordinate efforts. Establishing these relationships was vital to placing the office within the existing university landscape in a way that respected the roles of other entities. Finding champions

was another crucial strategy. The support of the dean of computer science, for example, significantly boosted the OSPO's credibility and reach.

The “open source as an alternative” approach has helped integrate the OSPO into the university's broader open science efforts. It has developed a unique identity that resonates well with its interdisciplinary and neutral stance, serving all university divisions without bias. This strategic positioning helped avoid the anchoring effect that might occur when open source efforts are embedded within a specific department.

Making change happen

The complexity of university research administration means that different departments play various roles in managing commercialization efforts, requiring a clear understanding of each entity's responsibilities and occasional overlap in their functions. Researchers may approach the OSPO with a piece of open source software they wish to commercialize, but certain aspects such as legal issues and commercialization fall outside its scope.

In terms of success stories, Choudhury mentions the Open Energy Outlook project associated with the Scott Institute at CMU, which explores the impact of decarbonization policies. The OSPO assisted this project by evaluating its engineering state, licensing questions, and proposal support. They also connected the project with organizations like the Eclipse Foundation and the Linux Foundation's energy group. Similarly, for the Penrose project, which aids in visualizing mathematical concepts, the OSPO provided support with community building, governance, and financial management advice, illustrating the kind of help people can get for their initiatives towards greater impact.

Another area of action for the OSPO is working with students. Student groups working on open source projects face various challenges, particularly the issue of leadership transition as members graduate. The OSPO proposes solutions such as using GitHub Enterprise to manage project rights and ensure continuity. This broad support encompasses organizing and sponsoring hackathons, providing infrastructure, and guiding students on how to manage, share, and sustain their projects. The overall aim is to foster a robust environment for open source software development and community building, benefiting both individual projects and the broader academic community.

OSPOs and research assessment

The OSPO's role as a reference for researchers is clear. But can the OSPO work internally, changing research incentives to foster open source work? In this aspect, Choudhury makes a direct link between open source software and social impact, particularly the sustainable development goals. A collaboration between CMU and University of Pittsburgh shows how open source tools are used to address real-world problems, such as monitoring air pollution, which has broader implications for public health.

Impact is a hard dimension to track, but key for open source. Traditional collaborations between universities are typically mediated by specific legal agreements, in contrast with the more seamless collaboration facilitated by open source software. Through licensing, open source projects enable broader, more frictionless work, allowing contributions and usage from diverse sources while maintaining some level of control over the contributions. Choudhury mentions the key work of the [CHAOSS](#) Academic Working Group, discussing how to measure the impact of open source through metrics like research support, commercialization, curriculum, and social impact.

Assessing the landscape of open source projects within universities is challenging. At CMU there are efforts to streamline this through systematic approaches like using GitHub Enterprise. This platform would help inventory existing projects and analyze factors such as license choices, user contributions, and citations. Currently, foundational systems and infrastructure are being developed to create a comprehensive snapshot of these projects.

Recognizing the importance of open source in research assessment, CMU's Vice President for Research has expressed interest as part of a CMU Presidential Task Force focused on innovation and entrepreneurship. Choudhury mentions the importance of external support, such as [Sequoia Capital's open source fellowships](#), underscoring the growing recognition of open source contributions in academia.

Sustaining change

CMU is making significant efforts to incorporate open source software into the curriculum, particularly through a course taught by Steven Walli from Microsoft's Azure office. This course, initially developed at Johns Hopkins and now offered at CMU, focuses on software engineering at scale using open source tools. It aims to teach students how to build and deploy software professionally, mimicking real-world scenarios where software needs to perform reliably for thousands of users. The role of mentors from the open source projects and peer mentorship are particularly important. This initiative became crucial when tech sector layoffs rescinded summer internships for students, providing them with a valuable alternative learning experience.

The introduction of open source software in the educational context at CMU is also seen as a way to foster a culture of open science and collaboration. The open source framework allows for a more seamless integration of contributions and collaborations, bridging the gap between different universities and the private sector. This cultural shift is subtly implemented through supportive services, relationships, and practices that promote open science. Open source software serves as a practical entry point for discussions around open science, making it more accessible to faculty who may otherwise find the leap to open science daunting. This incremental approach aligns with broader institutional goals and global trends, such as the emphasis on open science by UNESCO and other policy frameworks.

CMU's leadership is actively engaging in strategic planning that incorporates open source and open science initiatives. The success of these efforts is being tracked through frameworks like the CHAOSS Academic Working Group to ensure consistency and collaboration across institutions. For now, anecdotal successes such as improved project transitions and better group functionality, highlight the positive impact of these initiatives. Choudhury closes by saying that the key is that open source projects at CMU are positioned as integral components of the university's broader strategic goals, ensuring they receive the necessary support and recognition to thrive.

How to cite this work

Experiences towards evidence-based policy for open science (annex). CERN-NASA Working Group “Incentives for Open Scholarship”. May 2024. Available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11395203>

This work is published under a CC BY 4.0 License.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Sean Sapcariu (FNR), Miriam Kip (BIH QUEST Center), Rob Hyndman (Monash University) and Sayeed Choudhury (Carnegie Mellon University) for their time and valuable contributions during interviews. We also want to thank members of the working group “Incentives for open scholarship” for their insights and productive discussions. Special thanks to the CERN Open Science team and the NASA TOPS initiative for their continuous support.

This work was funded by the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

